

PERSONALITY-ORIENTED TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *The article examines personality-oriented technologies for learning English, based on constructivist didactics. The importance of active cognitive activity of students, taking into account their individual abilities and interests, is emphasized. The role of the teacher as a mentor and consultant is described, contributing to the development of critical thinking, self-education skills, and teamwork among students. The "case study" method is provided as an example, which helps to form analytical skills, discussion, and joint problem-solving in English.*

Keywords: *personality-oriented, didactics, skill, self-education.*

Modern pedagogical technologies represent a fundamentally new approach to education, combining a personality-oriented paradigm with the ideas of self-realization and creativity of the individual. In Western pedagogy, this approach is referred to as constructive didactics. This direction of didactics rejects the traditional process of knowledge transmission (by a teacher or lecturer) and the passive reception of knowledge by the student. The core principle of constructivist didactics is to create conditions where knowledge and practical skills are acquired by learners through active cognitive activity, based on their individual abilities, interests, psychological, and characterological traits. In this case, knowledge and skills are more comprehensively and successfully developed, reaching the level of competencies, as they are formed in learners through meaningful creative activities. The implementation of this approach is only possible through various forms of productive activity, which include components such as student self-education and changes in the nature of communication between the teacher and students. This includes cooperation, support, and eventually, introducing students to the role of teaching assistants and consultants.

The main difference in next-generation educational programs lies in their subject-subject nature, where both the teacher and the student are equal participants in the educational process. The teacher takes on the role of an assistant, curator, consultant, and guide in the "endless labyrinth" of information.

The study of the dynamics of student learning and development is conducted not only through indicators such as the volume of information, its retention, and depth of understanding, but, more importantly, through the assessment of learning actions that the student will apply in the future.

In this approach, the learning process is focused not on passive memorization of information, but on developing thinking skills, self-education abilities, the capacity to reason, identify areas of "ignorance," and eliminate them through one's own efforts. Mastery of methods like induction and deduction is also emphasized.

The choice of teaching technologies is also aligned with the specifics of English language education and the acquisition of comprehensive foreign language skills by students. The effectiveness of the application of these technologies depends on the interaction between the

teacher and the students "within" each lesson. The quality of this interaction depends on a range of skills, including:

- Educational-cognitive skills – mastery of universal learning actions (ULA);
- Psychological skills – attention, focus, concentration, interest in communication, empathy;
- The ability to perceive and evaluate information presented both orally and in written form;
- The ability to grammatically formulate phrases and speech in a foreign (English) language;
- The ability to identify, analyze, and solve educational problems;
- The ability to participate in debates, discussions, and student conferences;
- The ability to work in a team;
- The ability to argue and defend one's idea, opinion, or point of view.

Case Study: The implementation of the "case study" technology should be introduced gradually into the educational process, specifically into particular lessons, as it requires a certain linguistic foundation and a relatively free command of spoken language. When it comes to professional business communication, it is advisable to model simple and small situations on topics that are understandable and interesting for the group. The goal of case study work is to solve a task through joint discussion of the situation and to develop teamwork skills. The theme of the situation allows each student to express their opinion and take part in developing a joint solution that will be presented for discussion. After familiarizing students with the content of the case, they are invited to express their opinion first in the form of a monologue and then participate in the discussion (dialogue), during which an optimal solution should be found.

During the application of case technology in the classroom, we took into account the stages of creating an educational speech situation – familiarization with the content of the situation, personal understanding, and students' speech activity.

Project. Project objectives: directing the actions of the project participants to work together in a team that will contribute to the development of competencies in self-organization of students.

The traditional general phases of the project: Putting forward a project idea. The beginning of the project. Implementation of the project. Presentation of the project results. Evaluation of the project.

Before starting the work, the students were familiarized with the criteria by which the results of the project will be evaluated:

- completeness of disclosure of the selected project topic;
- the construction of the project itself – compliance with the structure of educational project research, the presence of logical presentation of the material, linguistic literacy in grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, phrase construction, manner of presentation;
- meaningful answers to audience questions;
- the quality of illustrative material – presentations, slides (expediency and consistency of construction, reflection of key provisions and ideas of the project, systematization and organization of the material), a dictionary of new words and terms;
- the reaction and opinion of the audience (whether the topic was disclosed fully enough, informative and accessible). Did the presentation arouse interest?

In addition to obvious signs, "hidden effects" should be seen and taken into account - the development of communication skills, interpersonal relationships, verbal-linguistic and personal abilities of students, including those that they themselves did not suspect or did not attach

importance to them (visual memory, auditory memorization of words and perception of pronunciation).

Simulations. This technology is one of the interesting interactive teaching methods used in English classes at a non-linguistic university. According to many scientists, interactive methods contribute to increasing the activation of educational and cognitive activity of students, motivate them to learn a foreign language, and, as a result, raise the quality of education to a higher level. Taking into account the specifics of learning a foreign language, simulation means playing out an imaginary scene built to solve some educational task and language situation - for example, dating, shopping in a store, misunderstandings in transport, etiquette in a restaurant, theater, job interview, etc. Learning through simulation is aimed at expanding practical skills, improving interpersonal contacts in English. Problem-oriented simulations are very important from a pedagogical point of view, in which participants, as students or imaginary representatives of different social roles, discuss a problem and find ways to solve it.

Portfolio. A portfolio can confidently be considered an effective technology, as it combines a personalized approach with a reflective nature. It fosters self-development of the student through self-assessment, recording achievements and failures, self-analysis of mistakes or insufficient efforts, and an understanding of the lack of knowledge about effective learning methods to achieve set goals. Thus, a portfolio is not merely a list of completed tasks; it allows an evaluation of how the student organized the learning process (which principles guided their information search, the analysis of its reliability, relevance, and content appropriateness for the task at hand). Reflection begins from the very start of compiling the portfolio, as filling it requires answers to questions such as: What is my goal in studying this subject (English)? Where should I begin? How will I organize my work? As the portfolio is filled, the questions evolve: What are the results of my work? Am I satisfied with the results? How did I achieve this outcome? What gaps remain? What do I plan to do to improve my results?

In conclusion, personalized technologies in English language teaching are an effective tool not only for developing language competencies but also for important skills such as critical thinking, self-directed learning, teamwork, and problem-solving. The constructivist didactic approach emphasizes active cognitive activity, which contributes to students' comprehensive development. In this system, teacher plays the role of mentor and consultant, while the learning process is built on interaction and cooperation. Methods such as case studies immerse students in real-life situations, which in turn fosters a deeper understanding of the material and the development of practical skills. Ultimately, personalized technologies not only lead to successful language acquisition but also cultivate universal learning skills necessary for students' future professional and personal growth.

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